

MULTISCALE ANALYSIS TO INVESTIGATE THE MECHANICAL AND FORMING BEHAVIOUR OF HEMP FIBRE WOVEN FABRICS / POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibre composite is extensively used in automotive, aerospace, etc. industries recently by replacing synthetic fibre composites in certain applications due to the environmental concerns. In this study, hemp fibre woven fabrics based composites was investigated in different scale. Initially, hemp fibre dry yarns were studied and mechanical properties were obtained. Uniaxial tensile and tensile shear properties of hemp woven fabrics was also considered. Hemp fibre woven fabrics / polypropylene composite sheets was prepared by conventional thermal-compression process and mechanical properties of the composites was studied. Finally, composite sheets were formed to truncated conical shape to analyse the formability. It was observed that hemp fibre dry yarn, woven fabrics and composite provide good mechanical properties and composite sheets were given better formability too.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre composite utilization is significantly growing in different industries in the past years due to the environmental concerns. Natural fibres such as flax, hemp, jute, sisal, kenaf, etc. are widely used in the industries for the fabrication of composites [1]. Compared to the synthetic fibre composites, natural fibre composites have several advantages such as low density, low cost, non-abrasive while tooling, less health risk, low energy conception, recyclability, renewability, biodegradability, etc. They are light weight and they can provide good acoustic insulation properties. They are extensively used in automotive, aerospace, construction, etc. industries for engineering applications [2-4]. Oksman [5] fabricated flax / epoxy composites by resin transfer mould technique and mechanical properties of the composites were studied. Dhakal [6] studied the influence of water absorption effect on the mechanical properties of hemp fibre reinforced unsaturated polyester composites with different fibre volume fraction. Antony et al. [7-8] investigated the mechanical behaviour of hemp fibre dry yarns and hemp fibre woven fabrics based sandwich structures. Roe and Ansell [9] investigated the tensile, impact, inter-laminar shear properties of jute fibre / polyester composites. The mechanical properties of sisal / polypropylene composites and the effect of chemical treatment were studied by Joseph et al [10]. Karnani et al. [11] studied the mechanical properties and the effect of fibre orientation of kenaf fibre / Poly-L-lactic acid. As pointed out above, there are several studies in the past on natural fibre composites and most of the studies justify the expansion of natural composites in more engineering application. Despite they have some disadvantages like moisture absorption, low durability, limited processing temperature, high variability of properties, water ageing effect, etc. [1].

Researchers are focused on improving the quality of natural fibre composites recently by different methods and thereby enhance their utilization in different industrial applications. Banana, hemp and sisal fibres were esterified with maleic anhydride and increase in the mechanical properties between untreated and treated fibre novolac resin composite after steam, water absorption was found by Mishra et al. [12]. Toledo et al. [13] improved the durability of vegetable fibre reinforced mortar composites by several methods and immersion of fibres in silica fume slurry, early cure of composites in a CO₂-rich environment, etc. were found as better methods to improve the durability of the composite. Kumar [14] improved the thermal stability of bamboo/epoxy composite by adding the nanoclay. Yan et al [15]

studied the flax, linen, bamboo fabric/epoxy composites and influence of alkali treatment in the mechanical properties were investigated. It was found that alkali treatment increases the mechanical properties by improving the interfacial adhesion between fibres/epoxy. Tensile, flexural strength and stiffness of Jute/Epoxy composites were improved by silane treatment on fibre by Gassan et al. [16]. Alkali, silane and acetic anhydride chemical surface modifications were made for hemp-poly lactic acid composite by Oza et al. [17] and thermal degradation activation energy were characterized. It was observed that acetic anhydride treated hemp had 10-13% increase in the activation energy compared to other treated and untreated hemp fibre composites.

Hemp is an annual plant and the production of hemp plant is increasing steadily every year. Recently, the demand of the natural fibres has increased and the hemp fibres are cheap compared to other popular natural fibres for composite applications. In addition to that, hemp fibre straw is produced in a so-called 'total line' where the production of random non-aligned technical fibres together. Due to this, the raw material is readily available and it is attracted in automotive or aerospace industry where the production speed is very essential [18]. Polypropylene is one of the popular recyclable thermoplastic polymers and natural fibre have been widely used to reinforce polypropylene for industrial application, especially in automotive applications [19].

The aim of this work is to investigate hemp fibre woven fabrics based composites in different scale. Initially, hemp fibre dry yarns were studied and mechanical properties were obtained. Uniaxial tensile and tensile shear properties of hemp woven fabrics was also considered. Hemp fibre woven fabrics / polypropylene composite sheets was prepared by conventional thermal-compression process and mechanical properties of the composites was studied. Finally, composite sheets were formed to truncated conical shape to analyse the formability.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pure hemp yarns were produced by grinding, mechanical carding and spinning of textile hemp stem (length of 4/5 meters) and weaved into fabrics. Taffeta fabrics (plain weave) and serge (2x1) fabrics (twill weave) with an areal density of 290g/m² and 380g/m² respectively were utilized to fabricate the composites. Polypropylene sheet with a density of 0.91g/cm³, melt flow index of 3.2 (230^oC / 2.16kg) and thickness 0.8mm was used.

2.1 Hemp fibre dry yarn

Hemp fibre yarn specimens for tensile tests were prepared using a paper frame technique using thick paper and yarn specimens were attached using glue. Several specimens were prepared for each yarn with a gauge length $L_0 = 30\text{mm}$ (Figure 1). Tensile tests were performed with a static load under a cross-head speed $V = 1\text{mm/min}$ at ambient temperature using INSTRON 4411 machine.

Figure 1. Mechanical test setups of hemp fibre dry yarn: Uniaxial tensile test

2.2 Hemp fibre dry woven fabrics

Hemp fibre dry woven fabrics specimens for tensile, shear tests were prepared with a gauge length of 150mm and width of 25mm and for biaxial tensile tests were prepared with a cruciform shape having an arm width of 30mm and a total specimen gauge length of 60mm. (Figure 2). Tensile tests were performed with a static load under a cross-head speed $V = 3\text{mm/min}$ at ambient temperature using INSTRON 4411 machine.

Figure 2. Mechanical test setups of hemp fibre dry fabrics: (a) Uniaxial tensile and Tensile shear test, (b) Biaxial tensile test

2.3 Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite

Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite were fabricated by conventional thermal-press process. Fabrics were dried in oven at 160°C to avoid moisture and the hemp fabrics were placed between polypropylene sheets in a mould. The closed mould was placed in curing oven for 2 hour 30 minutes. The mould was pressed for 10 minutes with hydraulic thermal-press which was preheated for 2 hour 30 minutes. Specimens for tensile, shear tests were prepared with a gauge length of 150mm and width of 25mm and for biaxial tensile tests were prepared with a cruciform shape having an arm width of 30mm and a total specimen gauge length of 60mm. (Figure 3). Tensile tests were performed with a static load under a cross-head speed $V = 3\text{mm/min}$ at ambient temperature using INSTRON 4411 machine.

Figure 3. Mechanical test setups of hemp fibre fabrics/polypropylene composite: (a) Uniaxial tensile and Tensile shear test, (b) Biaxial tensile test

2.4 Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite sheet forming

Thermal-compression test was performed with a setup with mould, die and blank holder fixed inside an environmental chamber (Figure 4). The system was preheated for 2hrs and composite sheets were fixed. Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite sheet were formed at a temperature of 190°C into to truncated conical shape and formability was analysed.

Figure 4. Thermal-compression of hemp fibre fabrics/polypropylene composite

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the experimental analysis of hemp fibre yarn, hemp fibre woven fabrics, hemp fibre woven fabrics / polypropylene composite and hemp fibre composite sheet forming were mentioned and discussed below.

3.1 Hemp fibre dry yarn

The tensile stress versus tensile strain curves were plotted (Figure 5) and the tensile modulus, strength was calculated (Table 1). Tensile modulus of taffeta yarns in warp direction was 1046.62 ± 0.172 MPa and in weft direction was 1714.23 ± 0.135 MPa. Similarly, tensile modulus of serge (2x1) yarns in warp direction was 2746.14 ± 0.095 MPa and in weft direction was 3384.95 ± 0.301 MPa. Tensile strength of taffeta yarns in warp direction was 74.86 ± 6.42 MPa and in weft direction was 74.18 ± 4.79 MPa. Similarly, tensile strength of serge (2x1) yarns in warp direction was 167.71 ± 11.89 MPa in weft direction was 176.13 ± 9.99 MPa.

Specimen	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
<i>Taffeta yarn warp</i>	1046.62 ± 0.172	74.86 ± 6.42
<i>Taffeta yarn weft</i>	1714.23 ± 0.135	74.18 ± 4.79
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn warp</i>	2746.14 ± 0.095	167.71 ± 11.89
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn weft</i>	3384.95 ± 0.301	176.13 ± 9.99

Table 1: Mechanical properties of hemp fibre dry yarn

Figure 5. Tensile stress versus tensile strain of hemp fibre dry yarn

3.2 Hemp fibre dry woven fabrics

The tensile stress versus tensile strain curves were plotted (Figure 6) and the tensile modulus, strength was calculated (Table 2). Tensile modulus of taffeta fabrics in warp direction was $1415.22 \pm 0.082 \text{MPa}$ and in weft direction was $2342.42 \pm 0.153 \text{MPa}$. Similarly, tensile modulus of serge (2x1) fabrics in warp direction was $2428.33 \pm 0.119 \text{MPa}$ and in weft direction was $3980.65 \pm 0.199 \text{MPa}$. Tensile strength of taffeta fabrics in warp direction was $74.48 \pm 5.96 \text{MPa}$ and in weft direction was $69.00 \pm 5.21 \text{MPa}$. Similarly, tensile strength of serge (2x1) fabrics in warp direction was $119.10 \pm 10.89 \text{MPa}$ in weft direction was $125.69 \pm 3.66 \text{MPa}$. Shear stress versus shear strain curves were plotted (Figure 7) and the shear modulus, strength was calculated (Table 2). Shear modulus of taffeta fabrics was $632.73 \pm 15.84 \text{MPa}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $821.44 \pm 21.42 \text{MPa}$. Shear strength of taffeta fabrics was $30.73 \pm 4.02 \text{MPa}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $46.21 \pm 5.62 \text{MPa}$. Biaxial-tensile force versus displacement curves were plotted (Figure 8) and the maximum biaxial-tensile force was calculated (Table 2). Maximum biaxial-tensile force of taffeta fabrics was $1168.71 \pm 25.65 \text{N}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $3001.35 \pm 32.64 \text{N}$.

Figure 6. Tensile stress versus tensile strain of hemp fibre dry fabrics

Figure 7. Shear stress versus shear strain of hemp fibre dry fabrics

Figure 8. Maximum biaxial force versus displacement of hemp fibre dry fabrics

Specimen	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Shear modulus (MPa)	Shear strength (MPa)	Maximum biaxial force (N)
<i>Taffeta yarn warp</i>	1415.22±0.082	74.48±5.96	632.73±15.84	30.73±4.02	1168.71±25.65
<i>Taffeta yarn weft</i>	2342.42±0.153	69.00±5.21			
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn warp</i>	2428.33±0.119	119.10±10.89	821.44±21.42	46.21±5.62	3001.35±32.64
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn weft</i>	3980.65±0.199	125.69±3.66			

Table 2: Mechanical properties of hemp fibre dry fabrics

3.3 Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite

The tensile stress versus tensile strain curves were plotted (Figure 9) and the tensile modulus, strength was calculated (Table 3). Tensile modulus of taffeta fabrics in warp direction was 1143.50±45.38MPa

and in weft direction was $1356.81 \pm 33.61 \text{ MPa}$. Similarly, tensile modulus of serge (2x1) fabrics in warp direction was $1871.80 \pm 32.31 \text{ MPa}$ and in weft direction was $1233.40 \pm 22.65 \text{ MPa}$. Tensile strength of taffeta fabrics in warp direction was $25.67 \pm 3.45 \text{ MPa}$ and in weft direction was $28.13 \pm 2.78 \text{ MPa}$. Similarly, tensile strength of serge (2x1) fabrics in warp direction was $40.93 \pm 5.89 \text{ MPa}$ in weft direction was $26.52 \pm 3.44 \text{ MPa}$. Shear stress versus shear strain curves were plotted (Figure 10) and the shear modulus, strength was calculated (Table 3). Shear modulus of taffeta fabrics was $417.29 \pm 12.34 \text{ MPa}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $518.61 \pm 11.31 \text{ MPa}$. Shear strength of taffeta fabrics was $12.13 \pm 2.17 \text{ MPa}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $14.59 \pm 2.65 \text{ MPa}$. Biaxial-tensile force versus displacement curves were plotted (Figure 11) and the maximum biaxial-tensile force was calculated (Table 3). Maximum biaxial-tensile force of taffeta fabrics was $3461.75 \pm 46.29 \text{ N}$ and serge (2x1) fabrics was $4171.82 \pm 52.41 \text{ N}$.

Figure 9. Tensile stress versus tensile strain of hemp fibre woven fabrics / Polypropylene composite

Figure 10. Shear stress versus shear strain of hemp fibre woven fabrics / Polypropylene composite

Figure 11. Maximum biaxial force versus displacement of hemp fibre woven fabrics / Polypropylene composite

Specimen	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Shear modulus (MPa)	Shear strength (MPa)	Maximum biaxial force (N)
<i>Taffeta yarn warp</i>	1143.50±45.38	25.67±3.45	417.29±12.34	12.13±2.17	3461.75±46.29
<i>Taffeta yarn weft</i>	1356.81±33.61	28.13±2.78			
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn warp</i>	1871.80±32.31	40.93±5.89	518.61±11.31	14.59±2.65	4171.82±52.41
<i>Serge (2x1) yarn weft</i>	1233.40±22.65	26.52±3.44			

Table 3: Mechanical properties of hemp fibre woven fabrics / Polypropylene composite

3.4 Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite sheet forming

Hemp fibre woven fabrics / polypropylene composite sheets were formed into truncated conical by thermal-compression process shape (Figure 12). As the formability is the ability of material to form into different temperature, it is essential to analyse it. The utilization of blank holder avoided the wrinkling of the sheets and better quality final product were obtained. The formability of the composite sheets was analysed and it was observed that the hemp composite polypropylene sheets can be formed into desired shape by thermal-compression process comfortably.

Figure 12. Hemp fibre woven fabrics/Polypropylene composite sheet formed to truncated conical shape

4 CONCLUSION

Uniaxial-tensile properties of hemp fibre dry yarns were investigated and tensile properties were calculated. Similarly, uniaxial tensile, tensile shear and biaxial tensile properties of hemp fibre woven dry fabrics were studied and the mechanical properties were estimated. Hemp fibre woven fabrics/polypropylene composites sheets were manufactured by thermal press process and mechanical test were performed to investigate the uniaxial tensile, tensile shear and biaxial tensile properties. The hemp composite sheets were formed into truncated conical by thermal-compression process shape and better formability of the composite sheets were observed.

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